

Removal of lead(II) from aqueous solutions using rice bran : an agricultural waste

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Abstract : In present work, the agricultural waste rice bran is used as an adsorbent for the removal of lead(II) from aqueous solutions. The adsorption characteristics of lead(II) on rice bran were evaluated as a function of pH, temperature, contact time and initial metal concentration. The effective adsorption was found in the pH range 3.5–4.5. The results reveal that adsorption of lead(II) onto rice bran is up to 69% at 100 min adsorption contact time. The optimum temperature for lead(II) adsorption was found to be 25 °C. The adsorption data fitted well into Freundlich and Langmuir adsorption isotherm models. The results show that rice bran holds a great potential in removal of lead(II) from industrial wastewater.

Keywords : Lead(II), rice bran, Freundlich isotherm, Langmuir isotherm, wastewater.

Introduction

The problem of our ecosystem is increasing with the advancement in technology. Heavy metal pollution is one of these problems. Toxic heavy metals release into the environment has been increasing continuously as a result of industrial activities and technological development. The release of these heavy metals possess significant threat to the environment and public health because of their toxicity, bioaccumulation in the food chain and persistence in nature¹. Pollution and toxicity of lead to human and aquatic life is well documented^{2–4}. Lead is one of the metals known to man since 2500 BC^{2,3}. Lead in the environment is strongly adsorbed by sediment and soil particles. Many of the inorganic salts of lead (lead oxide and sulfides) are not readily soluble in water and sequestered in sediments. In aquatic system uptake is influenced by various environmental factor such as temperature, salinity, pH and the presence of organic matters^{5,6}. Lead can pass through the placenta and thus affect a growing fetus. Organic lead compounds are fat soluble and are more toxic than other form⁷. The conventional methods of removal of lead from the aqueous environment include ion-exchange, lime softening, reverse osmosis coagulation and filtration. These methods are costly, not readily available

and environmental unfriendly⁸. Therefore, there is a need to develop new, cost effective and environmental friendly methods, including abundant and biodegradable materials for metal removal. A number of biomaterials have been used for removal of heavy metals ions from wastewater^{9–12}.

The main purpose of this study was to investigate the adsorption properties of rice bran for removal of lead(II). The study included the observation of influence of pH, temperature, contact time and examination of adsorption behavior of rice bran.

Results and discussion

Effect of pH :

The adsorption of lead(II) on rice bran at different pH was performed using 1.25 mg L⁻¹ of lead(II) solution. The results shown in Fig. 1 depicts that the adsorption of the lead(II) increases as pH increases from 2 to 4.5. The maximum adsorption of metal was observed at pH 4.5. After pH 4.5 the metal adsorption decreases. The variation in removal efficiency due to the solution pH can be attributed to the precipitation of metal as hydroxide at a higher pH. This is similar to the finding of others where the interaction between oxygen free, Lewis basic sites

Fig. 1. Effect of pH on the removal of lead(II) on rice bran.

and the free electrons of anions as well as the electrostatic interaction between the anions the protonated sites of adsorbent are the main adsorption mechanisms¹³⁻¹⁵. The pH 4.5 was selected as optimum pH for biosorption of lead(II) for all studies.

Effect of contact time :

The adsorption of the lead(II) on rice bran increased with contact time to reach its maximum adsorption at or after 100 min, after that reaches equilibrium. Hence the contact time of 100 min was set for all experiments. At the initial stage the rate of removal of lead(II) was higher up to 40 min due to availability of more than required number of active sites on the surface of adsorbent and became slower at later stage of contact time, due to the decreased or lesser number of active sites¹⁶. This result is important as equilibrium time is one of the important parameter for an economical wastewater treatment system.

Effect of temperature :

Adsorption studies were carried out at temperatures 15, 25 and 35 °C. The adsorption efficiency increased on increasing temperature from 15 to 25 °C but after increasing temperature from 25 to 30 °C decrease in adsorption efficiency was observed. Maximum adsorption of lead(II) occurs at 25 °C.

Biosorption equilibrium studies :

The biosorption equilibrium uptake (Q_e , mg metal g⁻¹ biomass dry wt.) for each sample was calculated according to the mass balance of metal ion, expressed as :

$$Q_e = V(C_0 - C_e)/M \tag{1}$$

where, V is the sample volume (L), C_0 , the initial metal ion concentration (mg L⁻¹), C_e , the equilibrium or final concentration (mg L⁻¹) and M , the biomass dry weight (g).

Adsorption isotherm data were also fitted to the classical Freundlich and Langmuir isotherm equations¹⁷. The linearized forms of isotherm equations used are :

Freundlich equation :

$$\log Q_e = \log K + 1/n \log C_e \tag{2}$$

where Q_e is the equilibrium metal uptake capacity and C_e , the residual metal concentration at equilibrium. The constant K is a measure of adsorption capacity and $1/n$ is the intensity of adsorption. A plot of $\log Q_e$ versus $\log C_e$ as shown in Fig. 2 gives a straight line of slope $1/n$ and intercepts $\log K$. The correlation coefficient (R^2) was found to be 0.9584.

Langmuir equation :

$$1/Q_e = 1/Q_{max} b \times 1/C_e + 1/Q_{max} \tag{3}$$

where, Q_{max} represent the maximum specific metal uptake C_e , the residual metal concentration at equilibrium and b the ratio of adsorption/desorption rates related to energy of adsorption. The capacity of rice bran for binding with lead(II) was determined by plotting C_e/Q_e against C_e , using the Langmuir equation. The plot of the specific sorption C_e/Q_e against equilibrium concentration C_e shown in Fig. 3 gave the linear isotherm parameters Q_{max} and b . The correlation coefficient (R^2) was found to be 0.9488.

Freundlich and Langmuir adsorption isotherm parameters

Fig. 2. Freundlich plot for adsorption of lead(II) on rice bran at 25 °C.

Fig. 3. Langmuir plot for adsorption of lead(II) on rice bran at 25 °C.

are given in Table 1. It was observed that the adsorption equilibrium data fitted well for both Freundlich and Langmuir isotherms in the concentration range 5 to 100 mg L⁻¹.

Table 1. Freundlich and Langmuir adsorption constants for lead(II) using rice bran as adsorbent at 25 °C

Freundlich parameters		Langmuir parameters	
<i>K</i>	0.0637	<i>Q</i> _{mix} (mg g ⁻¹)	1.4468
<i>n</i>	1.5165	<i>b</i> (L mg ⁻¹)	0.0287
<i>R</i> ²	0.9584	<i>R</i> ²	0.9488

Experimental

Rice bran was collected from R.D. Industries (Rice mill), Jagdishpur, Gopalganj (Bihar) and was used in experiments by washing with double distilled water to re-

move the soluble lighter materials and drying at 65 °C in an oven. Standard stock solution (1000 mg L⁻¹) of lead(II) was prepared by dissolving lead nitrate (Analytical grade) in deionized water and required concentration of lead(II) was prepared by diluting stock solution with deionized water.

Batch experiments with rice bran were conducted to determine the parameters effect of the pH, temperature and contact time. The adsorption of 50 mL solution by 1.0 g rice bran was carried out in different glass bottles in a shaking thermostat at constant speed of 125 rpm. Then the solution was filtered and the filtrate containing the residual concentration of lead(II) was determined by atomic absorption spectrophotometer (ECIL-4141, Hyderabad). Studies were also conducted for the determination of effect of temperature (15, 25 and 35 °C) on metal sorption by rice bran from 50 mL solution of 1.25 mg L⁻¹ metal concentration. For the determination of rate of the metal biosorption by rice bran from 50 mL containing 1.25 mg L⁻¹ metal concentration, the filtrate was analyzed for residual lead(II) concentration after the contact period of 0, 20, 40, 60, 80, 100, 120 and 140 min. The effect of pH on the biosorption of lead by rice bran was determined at pH values of 2, 2.5, 3, 3.5, 4, 4.5, 5 and 5.5. The pH of the solution was maintained with 0.1 M HCl or 0.1 M NaOH. The sorption of lead(II) was carried out at different initial lead(II) concentration ranging from 5 to 100 mg L⁻¹ at optimum pH and speed of 125 rpm with the optimum agitation period by adding

1.0 g of rice bran. Freundlich, Langmuir isotherm and different constant were evaluated. The percent removal of lead(II) by rice bran was calculated using the equation :

$$\% \text{ Removal} = C_i - C_f / C_i \times 100 \quad (4)$$

where, C_i is the initial metal concentration in mg L^{-1} and C_f is the final concentration of the metal in mg L^{-1} .

Conclusions :

It has been proved rice bran is an excellent adsorbent for removal of Pb^{II} from aqueous solutions, under certain physiochemical conditions. The maximum adsorption can be obtained at 25 °C with in 100 min of contact time at pH 4.5. The results indicates the potentially practical value of rice bran as adsorbent like high adsorption capacity i.e. 1.4468 mg g^{-1} and also provide strong evidence to support the adsorption mechanism proposed. The comparison of rice bran with other adsorbents suggests that rice bran have a great potential application in environmental protection because of its cost effectiveness and easily availability as agricultural waste. Thus rice bran is an effective adsorbent for efficient removal of lead(II) from aqueous solution and it can be used as a cost effective adsorbent for the removal of lead(II) from industrial wastewater.

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